

*Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind Technology
Systems (FOWTs)*

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The MARINEWIND project aims to identify challenges and potential opportunities for enhancing the role of floating offshore wind technology in innovative system integration solutions. The project will explore market dynamics, policy and regulatory issues, social considerations, financial aspects, techno-economic solutions, and recommendations for storage and flexibility provisions.

This report presents the outcomes of the MARINEWIND 3rd Co-creation workshop in Portugal, organized on the 29th of May 2024 in Lisbon. The event, held in English under the title "*The Portuguese opportunity to go from innovation to industrialization in Floating Offshore Wind Technologies: analysing barriers and enablers.*", gathered a small but highly engaged group of 15 participants from various sectors, including Industry, Scientific & Research, Public authorities, Civil society, and Policy/Regulatory.

Organised in collaboration with the [Lisbon Energy Summit & Exhibition](#) at FIL - Lisbon Exhibition and Congress Centre, the workshop aimed to address the challenges of floating offshore wind energy, boosting the development of this technology. While Portugal has positioned itself as a leader in pioneering Floating Offshore Wind Technologies, the transition from innovation to industrialization presents several challenges. These include adapting the political and legal framework, improving support infrastructures, consolidating a national supply chain, strengthening and expanding the national grid and addressing environmental and social acceptance issues. The workshop provided a brief overview of each of these topics, exploring the Portuguese context and present status while highlighting some of the barriers and enablers. . Additionally, all participants contributed to identifying the main barriers and opportunities for the growth of floating wind energy in Portugal. They considering social, environmental, technological, and financial aspects, by participating in the MARINEWIND Mentimeter questionnaire and discussing the results during the event.

The event served as a platform for knowledge sharing and networking among industry experts, stakeholders, and participants, encouraging the formation of partnerships and connections to advance floating offshore wind technology.

The results of these discussions will be incorporated into the MARINEWIND web-based Geographical Information System (webGIS). This system will offer customized information about Floating Offshore Wind Turbines (FOWT) to stakeholders based on their category, location, and objectives. The system will also offer policy recommendations for informed Renewable Energy Sources (RES) policies and strategies to enhance societal acceptance (WP4). The Replicability Plan will facilitate the transfer of knowledge.

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1 EVENT DETAILS

EVENT LOCATION: FIL – Lisbon Exhibition and Congress Centre, Lisbon

EVENT DATE: 29th May 2024 14:00-16:30

EVENT TITLE: The Portuguese opportunity to go from innovation to industrialization in Floating Offshore Wind Technologies: analysing barriers and enablers

TYPE OF EVENT: Physical

CATEGORY OF THE EVENT: Co-creation Workshop

EVENT AFFILIATION: None

LEAD ORGANISER: WavEC Offshore Renewables

LANGUAGE: English

CONCEPT: The workshop targeted to bring together industry leaders, experts, and stakeholders to discuss and explore effective market measures for the transition from innovation to industrialization of floating offshore wind technologies in Portugal. This transition presents many challenges that are addressed during the event, including adapting the political and legal framework, improving support infrastructures, consolidating a national supply chain, strengthening and expanding the national grid and addressing environmental and social acceptance challenges. The event also aimed to strengthen collaboration between industry, academia, authorities, and the civil society sector, to accelerate and ensure the secure advancement of the floating wind industry towards successful commercial implementation.

OBJECTIVES

The workshop's specific objectives were to give an overview perspective of the main achievements of the MARINEWIND project during the first half of the project. The overview included the challenges, barriers, enablers and opportunities that Portugal might face to go from innovation to industrialization regarding the development of floating offshore wind technologies in the country. The discussion covered several aspects such as the political and legal framework, the necessary support infrastructures, the national supply chain, environmental and social acceptance challenges, and a special focus on the needs of strengthening and expanding the national grid. Active participation and discussion were facilitated through the MARINEWIND Mentimeter questionnaire, allowing participants to share their insights and perspectives.

As the two previous workshops in Portugal, the 3rd Co-Creation workshop was designed to contribute to the overall objectives of the MARINEWIND project:

- Increase awareness of FOWTs via co-creation activities that directly engage policy and decision makers, market and business actors, civil society organisations and funding bodies.
- Encourage social acceptance by directly involving local communities and fishermen and addressing environmental issues.

- Facilitate communication and collaboration among all the stakeholders directly and indirectly involved in the Portuguese MARINEWIND Lab.

TARGET AUDIENCE

The event targeted, in general, representatives of industry, research institutes, public authorities, supply chains, civil society, green innovation and policy and regulatory entities involved in the floating offshore wind sector.

For each specific category, the initial targeted audience included participants from:

- Industry: technology and project developers.
- Supply chain: port infrastructure, cable design and installation, tech/project developers, and trade associations, O&M services.
- Scientific & research community.
- Public authorities: at national level and maritime transport authorities.
- Policy/Regulatory: regulatory bodies at national level.
- Civil society: civil society organisations, citizens, and fisherman organizations.
- Green innovation: SMEs, ecologists.

AGENDA:

14:00-14:30 Welcome coffee

14:30-14:45 Presentation of the European MARINEWIND project by Janete Correia, Communication and Dissemination Coordinator of the project

14:45-15:15 Presentation *“Unlocking the potential of Floating Offshore Wind Technologies in Portugal - An overall analysis of barriers and enablers”*, by Paulo Chainho, Senior Offshore Electrical Engineer - WavEC Offshore Renewables

15:15-16:00 MARINEWIND Questionnaire: anonymous completion of an online questionnaire and visualisation and discussion of the results in real time with the aim of analysing the barriers and opportunities for implementing FOW projects in Portugal – Co-creation activity moderated by Paulo Chainho, Senior Offshore Electrical Engineer - WavEC Offshore Renewables, and Filipa Madureira, Communication Assistant – WavEC Offshore Renewables.

16:25-16:30 Closing and Coffee Break

PARTICIPANTS OF YOUR EVENT:

Figure 1 shows the target audience for the 3rd Co-creation MARINEWIND Workshop in Portugal (72 invitations), and Figure 2 shows the final audience that participated in the event (15 participants). For this workshop, apart from the invitations sent individually to the selected group of 72 stakeholders, the workshop was disseminated on WavEC’s and Lisbon Energy Summit’s communication platforms.

Figure 1. Initial target audience for the 3rd Co-creation MARINEWIND Workshop in Portugal (Lisbon).

Figure 2. Participants of the 3rd Co-creation MARINEWIND Workshop in Portugal (Lisbon).

2 OVERVIEW OF CONTRIBUTIONS AND INTERVENTIONS BY THE SPEAKERS

2.1 Relevance of the topics addressed in the 3rd Workshop in Portugal in the national floating offshore wind context

Portugal has prioritized the development of offshore wind resources within an energy policy framework that balances supply security, environmental sustainability, and economic feasibility. This focus began with the successful Windfloat and Windfloat Atlantic initiatives. The first initiative, a collaboration between EDP and Principle Power Inc. (PPI), involved a 2 MW wind turbine on a semi-submersible floating platform installed in 2011 off Póvoa de Varzim, proving the technology's viability. This success led to the Windfloat Atlantic project, the world's first semi-submersible offshore wind farm, installed in 2019 off Viana do Castelo with a total capacity of 25 MW from three 8.4 MW turbines. WindFloat Atlantic set a significant precedent for semi-submersible technology and spurred the development of an offshore energy cluster in Portugal. With recent advances in floating offshore wind, where Portugal has been a leader, the government aims to achieve 2 GW of installed capacity and auction 10 GW by 2030. This target supports broader goals to decarbonise the economy by 2050, increase renewable energy's share in electricity production to at least 85% by 2030, develop an offshore renewable energy market, and provide competitive prices for consumers. The decision to auction 10 GW of floating technologies by 2030 is due to the Portuguese continental shelf's narrow width and rapid depth increase, which make conventional fixed foundations unfeasible.

The Portuguese government is given firm steps towards the publication of the offshore wind auctions since the first semester of 2023. The most relevant advances are:

- **Jan/2022:** Decree Law 15/2022 creates the Viana do Castelo Technological Free Zone (ZTL) to promote ocean renewable energy development at prototype and pre-commercial stages, providing a dedicated area, infrastructure, and simplified licensing procedures.
- **Sep/2022:** Creation of an interministerial Working Group to evaluate the possibility of having up to 10 GW of offshore wind auctioned until 2030 (identifying suitable lease areas, proposing auction timelines and models, assessing grid requirements, and evaluating port infrastructure needs).
- **Jun/2023:** The working group released the final report, suggesting a first-round auction of 3.5GW. The final lease areas for offshore wind were proposed, to be followed by a public consultation period.
- **Oct/2023:** Opened a period for expressing interest (Eol) in participating in a competitive auction for developing renewable offshore projects, with 49 entities submitting their interest.
- **Dec/2023:** The public consultation period for the final lease areas ended, registering 148 participations. Comments are still being reviewed in May 2024, with the final areas to be included in the Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP).
- **Jan-Fev/2024:** The Government invited the entities who expressed interest (Eol) in participating in the auctions for a dialogue and clarification session.
- **Mar/2024:** Portuguese legislative elections resulted in the election of a new government.
- **Apr/2024:** The new Portuguese government requested REN (national TSO) to develop investments plans for the transmission grid (PDIRT-E) aligning with National Energy and Climate Plans (NECP2030).

The plan draft, released last year, includes 2GW offshore wind installed and 10 GW auctioned by 2030, final version to be submitted in June.

- **May 2024:** During the event Lisbon Energy Summit, of which this 3rd Workshop was part of as a side event, the government announced that updates on offshore wind energy auction to be announced soon.
- **September 2024:** Submission of the final version of the National Energy and Climate Plan (PNEC) revision to the European Commission, aiming to align national energy and climate goals; the draft version indicated 2 GW of offshore wind installed capacity by 2030.

The audience expected to be present at the Lisbon Energy Summit was not familiar with floating offshore wind technologies and was more knowledgeable about general energy issues. The 3rd Co-Creation Workshop was designed considering the expected attendance to the Lisbon Energy Summit event and the aspects that were already covered by the two previous Co-Creation Workshops organized in Portugal in an attempt to complement the topics already discussed in previous workshops. The 1st Co-Creation Workshop centered the discussion on the needs to adapt and develop new port infrastructure to support the developments on FOWTs announced by the Portuguese government. The 2nd Co-Creation Workshop analyzed the design and criteria of the offshore wind auctions, including non-price criteria. Another aspect taken into consideration to design the 3rd Workshop was the relevant MARINEWIND results in identifying barriers, challenges, opportunities, and enablers in different aspects for the development of FOWTs in the country achieved until May 2024. In view of all the above points, it was decided to design the 3rd Co-Creation Workshop to disseminate the main results reached in the MARINEWIND project up to the date of the event and analyze the upgrades and reinforcements that will be needed in the national grid infrastructure to integrate the energy produced by the offshore wind energy developments planned for the coming decades.

2.2 Results of the Presentation “Unlocking the potential of Floating Offshore Wind Technologies in Portugal - An overall analysis of barriers and enablers.”

Paulo Chainho’s presentation addressed several key aspects of developing floating offshore wind technologies (FOWT) in Portugal. It began with an overview of the progress made in this area within the country and continued with a detailed analysis of the Portuguese context. This included examining the barriers and enablers to FOWT development, considering factors such as the political and legal framework, environmental challenges, port infrastructure, the national supply chain, and grid connections.

Track record

The successful track record is based on the development of the Windfloat and Windfloat Atlantic projects. Since the initial pre-feed studies for the Windfloat Prototype in 2009, the country has accumulated vast experience on FOWTs and hosted the development of an emerging offshore energy cluster in Portugal.

Political and legal framework

Portugal motivation for developing offshore wind energy stems from its decarbonization goals, economic development objectives, and the aim to achieve a stable energy production mix, by

increasing the share of renewable energy (RE) in electricity production. Under the National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP), Portugal is committed to reaching at least 85% RE in electricity production by 2030. Electricity consumption is also expected to rise significantly, influenced by hydrogen production estimates.

The licensing process was presented, giving details of the procedures, licenses and key authorities involved. These include:

- 1) The Reserved Capacity Title (TRC) that grants the right to use a specified power capacity within the Public Electrical Grid, and Private Use of Maritime Space (TUPEM) that grants the right to use a specific area at the national maritime space;
- 2) Production License, which is a formal authorization enabling the holder to construct and operate a power generation plant in compliance with energy and environmental policies;
- 3) Operation license, that authorizes the power plant to connect to the public electrical grid, requiring a compliance inspection and alignment with production license terms and applicable regulations.

Environmental challenges

Portugal's early implementation of FOWT projects has provided the country with valuable experience in assessing the environmental impacts from offshore wind projects. This experience is vital for ensuring the sustainable development of future projects. Criteria for sustainable FOWTs will include environmental impact assessment (EIA), mitigation measures that imply technological innovations and operational solutions to minimize the impact, compensation and restoration measures, cumulative impact assessment, and circularity of materials. For offshore projects to be developed in Portugal, an EIA is required for power capacity above 50 MW or for more than 20 turbines' project, or above 20 MW or 10 turbines if located in sensitive areas.

Port Infrastructures

Port infrastructures play a relevant role throughout the lifecycle of a FOW project. Ports serve as assembly sites for the floating wind turbines, serve also as storage and transportation hubs for the offshore equipment, and are the starting point for the operation and maintenance of the offshore wind farms.

The interministerial Working Group created in September 2022 analyzed the readiness of the Portuguese Ports to support FOW developments and concluded that, despite its potential, national port infrastructure has significant limitations. Ports such as Viana, Aveiro, Figueira da Foz, Setúbal, and Sines have the potential to support FOW activities, but need upgrades, while others like Leixões and Lisboa face significant restrictions due to existing concessions or lack of space. Therefore, infrastructure upgrades are crucial to support the development of this industry, with a projected timeline for development between 5 to 7 years.

Supply Chain

Portugal's established onshore wind industry and strong industrial sectors, like metalworking and cement, position the country to develop a competitive offshore wind sector. The potential for forming an industrial cluster is significant, although the current capacity is insufficient to meet future demands.

Grid Connections

The Portuguese transmission grid will need significant investments to support the offshore wind capacity, especially as it exceeds 2.5 GW. Potential solutions include radial topology, where each wind farm is connected to the shore individually using its own dedicated export cable, or adopting a hub topology for the offshore network, which offers flexibility and reduces the number of cables to shore. Ownership models for the offshore transmission system are still being discussed, with comparisons drawn between the UK's competitive tendering model and Germany's TSO-centric model.

Conclusions

Portugal has a strong track record in FOWT and clear political support for developing this sector. However, challenges remain in environmental impacts, port infrastructure, supply chain development, and grid connections. Addressing these challenges effectively could position Portugal as a leader in the floating offshore wind industry, capitalizing on both national and global market opportunities.

2.3 Presentation of the European MARINEWIND project

The presentation of the MARINEWIND project was conducted by Janete Correia (WavEC). The following topics were included and presented during this part of the event:

- Promotional MARINEWIND video
- Composition of the MARINEWIND Consortium.
- Ambition of the project.
- Methodology and duration of the project.
- Location of the 5 Labs (Portugal, UK, Greece, Italy, and Spain), highlighting the importance of the different developing phases in the implementation of FOWTs of each country, and how it is expected that Labs will support the transfer of knowledge from the established experiences to the potential FOWT sites where plans for installation of FOWT are still at various stages of planning or implementation.
- Presentation of the most relevant projects or initiatives of each Lab.
- Presentation of the progress of the MARINEWIND Project (main public deliverables to be available soon on the website, number of workshops conducted until May 2024, etc.)
- Introduction to the Co-creation activity in the MENTIMETER Tool.

3 CO-CREATION ACTIVITY

A survey was prepared by APRE, RSE, CNR and UoY on the MENTIMETER Tool to be submitted to all the participants during the three Workshop events of the MARINEWIND Labs. This data collection exercise was intended to provide an insightful data of participants' experiences and insights regarding barriers and enablers for the implementation of floating offshore wind in Portugal.

3.1 Results of the survey

Question 1 - Which of the following categories represents you?

Figure 3. MENTIMETER Tool Question 1 results.

The question regarding the category to which the participants belonged highlighted a greater audience from the business sector (6), followed by an overall balance in the participation between institutions (1), research centres (2) and “other” category (2).

Question 2 - What are the most important enabling factors to invest in FOWTs?

Figure 4. MENTIMETER Tool Question 2 results.

This question received votes from 10 participants. A “Clear regulatory framework” was the answer with more votes (6) followed by “Presence of incentives” (2), “Potential for local supply chain development”

(1) and “Technological maturity (platform, dynamic cables)” (1). “Stability of the national transmission grid” and “Large market share and demand” were not selected.

Question 3 - Where is the most significant risk in your value chain, in your opinion?

Figure 5. MENTIMETER Tool Question 3 results.

The “development of adequate infrastructures (e.g., ports)” was the most significant risk associated with the value chain chosen by the audience with 8 votes out of 11. “Capacity of the supply chain at the local level” received 2 votes, and “Availability of ad hoc vessels for the installation of the turbines” was voted by 1 participant.

Question 4 – How can the industry engage with the local communities and stakeholders to address concerns related to the development of FOWTs? Prioritise the actions

Figure 6. MENTIMETER Tool Question 4 results.

In this question, the audience was asked to order, by the level of importance, the actions that could help the industry to engage with the local communities and stakeholders to address concerns related to the deployment of FOWTs. With 11 answers, the final order revealed that people consider “Inform the local community about FOWT financial benefits (e.g. new job opportunities)” the most effective

action. “Promote inclusive decision-making (e.g. townhall meetings, public consultations)” for the second place followed by “Establishing partnerships with local and public organisations”, “Share environmental and socioeconomic studies”, “Implement community outreach & educational programmes (e.g. workshops, lectures)”, “Propose biodiversity recovery plans, environmental benefits and safety measures” and “Update the local community about the pilot results (e.g. platforms, prototypes)”

Question 5 - What are the key environmental concerns associated with FOWTs? Prioritise the concerns included in the following list

Figure 7. MENTIMETER Tool Question 5 results.

In this question, which allowed each person to choose one to three options, were identified three key environmental concerns associated with FOWTs: “Impact on marine ecosystems (e.g. reduction of biodiversity)” with 9 votes, “Habitat degradation/modification” with 7 votes, and “Noise, electromagnetic fields, heat, pollution” with 4 votes. All other answers got 2 votes each: “Collision with structures”, “Possible spills”, “Sediment resuspension”, “Hydrodynamic changes” and “Visual impact of FOWTs”.

Question 6 – What infrastructure challenges need to be addressed to support the growth of the floating offshore wind industry?

Figure 8. MENTIMETER Tool Question 6 results.

Like the previous question, here each person was allowed to choose one to three options. There were two clear winners regarding infrastructure challenges that need to be addressed to support the growth of the FOW sector in Portugal: “Invest in adequate port infrastructures for the logistics, installation and maintenance phases” with 9 votes and “Enhance grid connectivity and transmission infrastructure”

with 7 votes. The remaining votes went to: “Overcome challenges in the supply chain” (4), “Standardization of new solutions” (3), “Scalability of current solutions to commercial scale” (2), “Technological maturity” (2), “Stability of the electrical network” (2) and “Invest in piloting and testing phases” (1)

Question 7 – What strategies can be employed to build trust and acceptance among communities where these technologies are being deployed?

Figure 9. MENTIMETER Tool Question 7 results.

In this question, again, each person was allowed to choose one to three options. 11 participants replied to the question “What strategies can be employed to build trust and acceptance among communities where these technologies are being deployed?” The answers with more votes were “Implement benefit-sharing mechanisms, such as community investment funds or local job creation initiatives” (9), “Foster public participation” (7), and “Encourage and support local businesses to provide operations and maintenance solutions” (6), followed by. “Increase environmental studies” (4), “Define fishing areas/zones” (4), “Propose biodiversity recovery plans” (1), Minimize sea use and co-existing conflicts (1) and “Develop metrics to assess participation and make these part of project evaluations” (1).

Question 8 - Which activity is most in conflict with the floating offshore wind sector?

Figure 10. MENTIMETER Tool Question 8 results.

Regarding which activity is most conflicting with the offshore wind sector, “fishing” got the first place, closely followed by “environmental protection”, which was by followed “shipping”. “Tourism” came in fourth place.

Question 9 - Which activity is most compatible with the floating offshore wind sector?

Figure 11. MENTIMETER Tool Question 9 results.

In this question, the audience was asked to score each option, from zero to ten, in accordance with its compatibility with the FOW sector. When asked about “Which activity is most compatible with the floating offshore wind sector?”, the audience agreed that “Tourism” is the most compatible, followed by “Environmental protection” and “Shipping”. The less compatible activity chosen is “Fishing” and “Other”.

Question 10 - What kind of impact do you think floating offshore wind farms could have on local economic activities (e.g., fishing, tourism)?

Figure 12. MENTIMETER Tool Question 10 results.

When participants were asked about the kind of impact of floating offshore wind farms on local economic activities, 20 attendees replied the following: “Positive impact” (4), “Moderately positive impact” (3), “Strong positive impact” (2) and “Moderately negative impact” (2).

Question 11 - What kind of impact do you think floating offshore wind farms could have on the environment (e.g., biodiversity)?

Figure 13. MENTIMETER Tool Question 11 results.

When participants were asked about the kind of impact of floating offshore wind farms on the environment, 10 attendees replied the following: “Moderately negative impact” (5), “Positive impact” (2), “Moderately positive impact” (2) and “Negative impact” (1).

Question 12 - Do you think that floating offshore wind farms could bring benefits to the local community (e.g., economic benefits and energy savings, improvement of air quality, general improvement of quality of life)?

Figure 14. MENTIMETER Tool Question 12 results.

When participants were asked “Do you think that floating offshore wind farms could bring benefits to the local community?”, 11 attendees replied. The majority stated, “I strongly agree” (5) and “I agree” (5). 1 attendee voted “I slightly agree”.

4 DISCUSSIONS TOPICS OVERVIEW

The group of the 3rd workshop was small but very dynamic and participative. One of the discussions emphasized the importance of prioritizing community outreach and educational programs to foster positive decision-making, highlighting the need to share environmental and socio-economic studies for informed decisions. Participants stressed the significance of local community partnerships and employment opportunities, raising concerns about the impacts on local communities without proper studies and feedback collection.

Various environmental issues related to marine wind projects were also discussed, including electromagnetic fields, habitat degradation, and visual effects, underscoring the need for more research and funding. The challenges of obtaining and analyzing data due to funding limitations were highlighted, with an emphasis on independent scientific research to avoid conflicts of interest.

Technological readiness and commercialization were debated, with concerns about the costs and risks of scaling up technologies to commercial levels. The need for significant infrastructure development to support marine wind projects was also discussed, emphasizing the importance of developing local industries and skills, and the potential for job creation and economic benefits. They also highlighted successful case studies and previous projects that demonstrated the importance of thorough environmental monitoring and community engagement.

Strategies to build trust and acceptance among local communities were considered crucial for the success of marine wind projects, along with discussions on the potential economic benefits and energy savings for local communities. Participants explored the importance of transparent communication and engagement to address community concerns effectively. One experienced participant of the marine renewable energy sector further elaborated on the importance of involving local stakeholders from the outset to ensure that projects are tailored to the specific needs and contexts of the communities they impact.

The discussion also covered the significant infrastructure development needed to support marine wind projects. Emphasis was placed on the potential for job creation and economic growth by developing local industries and skills to support the marine wind sector. The experienced participant shared that despite the ambitious targets, the readiness of the industry, including the development of ports and transport facilities, remains a challenge.

The collaborative atmosphere and diverse perspectives contributed to a comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted challenges and opportunities in implementing marine wind projects, underlining the critical need for coordinated efforts and continuous dialogue among stakeholders.

5 SUMMARY OF IDENTIFIED BARRIERS AND ENABLERS

The table below summarises the main barriers, criticalities and bottlenecks identified during the 3rd Workshop on the left column, and the most significant enablers and incentives on the right column. Some of the barriers and enablers were already identified during the 1st and 2nd Co-Creation Workshops in Portugal.

BARRIERS	ENABLERS
Maritime Spatial Plan (MSP) has not yet been updated with the new areas for offshore wind (consultation period ended in Dec/2023). Crucial step to initiate the auctions.	There is already experience in Portugal in accessing the environmental impacts of the novel sector of FOWTs.
Offshore wind farms can have visual and aesthetic impacts, which may be a concern for coastal communities and tourism industries.	As a late adopter of large offshore wind developments, Portugal can implement best practices and proven regulatory frameworks from North Sea transmission networks.
Uncertainty regarding the political environment.	Opportunity to modernize and enhance the national grid (e.g. offshore HVDC corridors).
FOWRs can have various impacts on marine species, including fish, marine mammals, and seabirds.	The national port infrastructure benefit from natural conditions that may be developed to accommodate FOW requirements.
Offshore substations in deep waters (technical solutions are not yet available).	The prospect of a medium to long-term plan for the FOW sector has the potential to catalyze significant investments in port infrastructure.
Regulatory and policy framework definition can be challenging.	There is a global lack of industrial capacity to meet the ambitious targets for offshore wind deployments, which provides an opportunity for attracting industrial developments in Portugal.
At the present, no existing infrastructure is able to support the development of large scale floating offshore wind projects, constraining immediate deployment.	Significant contribution to decarbonisation of the energy system (<i>identified too during the 2nd Workshop</i>).
The timeline for upgrading port infrastructure is challenging, with some sources estimating a duration of 5-7 years.	Recent advances in Portugal to create a clearer regulatory framework for the implementation of offshore wind projects (<i>identified too during the 1st and 2nd Workshops</i>).

<p>No experience with offshore wind energy auctions (<i>identified too during the 2nd Workshop</i>).</p>	<p>Successful track record in national and international supply chain integration for the Windfloat Atlantic project (<i>identified too during the 2nd Workshop</i>).</p>
<p>Non-availability of raw materials (copper, steel, etc.) can delay project delivery (<i>identified too during the 2nd Workshop</i>).</p>	<p>National planning supporting the implementation of offshore wind energy on the medium and long term (<i>identified too during the 1st and 2nd Workshop</i>).</p>
<p>Lack of enough internal technical/industrial capacity to meet the future needs of the offshore wind industry (<i>identified too during the 1st and 2nd Workshops</i>).</p>	<p>Environment sanctuaries that promote biodiversity created by wind farms when no other activities are allowed in the wind farm maritime space (<i>identified too during the 1st and 2nd Workshops</i>).</p>

6 ANNEX – PHOTOS

